

A Novel Polar Zinc-based Hybrid Material: Structure, Properties, and Memristive Performance

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Abstract text: Memristors are promising components for neuromorphic computing because of their resistive switching and synaptic functionalities, enabling more energy-efficient computing architectures. Lead halide perovskites are attractive memristive materials due to their coupled ionic-electronic conductivity, but lead toxicity limits their practical use. Herein, we report a new lead-free hybrid zinc halide, $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ (CHA = cyclohexylammonium), synthesized through a simple, scalable, and environmentally friendly route. Single-crystal X-ray diffraction shows that the compound crystallizes in a non-centrosymmetric structure composed of isolated $(\text{ZnI}_4)^{2-}$ tetrahedra separated by CHA cations, resembling Ruddlesden–Popper phases despite its zero-dimensional nature. Although the material is polar, no ferroelectric behavior is observed due to dominant electrical losses, likely related to its relatively narrow 2.3 eV band gap. Memristors based on $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ exhibit stable and reproducible electroforming-free resistive switching at low voltages, together with short- and long-term synaptic plasticity under

pulsed bias. These results establish $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ as a promising sustainable material for memory and neuromorphic applications and demonstrate the potential of Zn-based hybrid halides for advanced electronic devices.

1. Introduction

Traditional computing systems are currently limited by the von Neumann bottleneck, which creates an intrinsic "memory wall" and "power wall" due to the physical separation of processing and storage units, which entails low efficiencies and high energy consumptions for processing large amounts of data.^[1] The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) and the artificial intelligence (AI) is evidencing the urgent need for new alternative computing schemes, with higher efficiency and lower energy consumptions. Neuromorphic computing is seen as a potential alternative to traditional computing, since it is based on emulating the most efficient computing system known, the human brain. One of the critical elements within the neuromorphic hardware is the artificial synapses, which are electronic elements that mimic how the biological neurons communicate. In recent years, memristors have emerged as promising candidates to reproduce these artificial synapses, but finding an active material that meets the requirements for the practical application is still challenging. Lead-based halide perovskites are the state-of-the-art active materials in the field of memristors, as these materials exhibit excellent coupled ionic-electronic conductivity.^[2,3] Nevertheless, their low stability in ambient conditions and the toxicity of lead prevent their commercial application. The advancement of this technology demands more sustainable alternative materials with analogue properties and performance to lead halide perovskites.^[4]

Organic–inorganic metal halides (OIMHs) have emerged as a versatile class of materials with tunable structures and remarkable optoelectronic, dielectric, and ferroic properties.^[5] Their structural diversity arises from the combination of inorganic metal-halide units with organic cations, enabling architectures ranging from 3D frameworks to low-dimensional 0D discrete clusters. In particular, these low-dimensional OIMHs constructed from isolated or weakly connected metal-halide polyhedrons often exhibit strong exciton–lattice coupling, structural flexibility, pronounced dielectric responses, and reversible phase transitions. The combination of inorganic sublattices with organic components enables fine control over crystal symmetry, lattice dynamics, and intermolecular interactions. Their simple solution-based synthesis also enables scalable and low-cost fabrication, making them attractive for applications in lighting, sensing, energy storage, and information processing technologies.^[6]

While lead-based hybrid halides have long dominated the field due to their outstanding optoelectronic performance, increasing concerns regarding toxicity and long-term stability have driven an intense search for safer, lead-free alternatives.^[7–10] Among them, zinc-based hybrid halides have emerged as promising candidates due to the abundance, low toxicity, and non-critical nature of Zn^{2+} . Recent studies have demonstrated that zinc-based hybrid materials are not only safer but also highly versatile, significantly broadening the functional landscape of hybrid halides.^[11–16]

Structurally, Zn-based OIMHs are mainly zero-dimensional (0D) materials composed of isolated $[\text{ZnX}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra, with only one reported one-dimensional (1D) structure to this date to the best of our knowledge.^[17] This structural isolation leads to localized electronic states, self-trapped excitons, and defect-related luminescence.^[18–20] Beyond their luminescence properties, these materials can exhibit rich dielectric behavior and temperature-dependent structural phase transitions, often driven by the dynamics of the organic cations (usually vibrations and/or rotations), can involve reversible order–disorder or displacive mechanisms, leading to changes in lattice symmetry, conductivity, and permittivity^[21–23]. Such behavior highlights the strong coupling between the organic and inorganic sublattices. Some compounds also display thermosensitive effects, enabling direct conversion of thermal energy into mechanical motion.^[24] In addition, Zn-based OIMHs can exhibit multiferroicity, nonlinear optical activity, and piezoelectric energy harvesting capabilities.^[25–27] Structural distortions or symmetry breaking of the ZnX_4 tetrahedra can induce polarity and ferroelectric behaviour, including spontaneous polarization and switchable hysteresis loops.^[17,28] Together, these features highlight the potential of zinc-based hybrids for advanced functional devices.

Despite recent advances, Zn-based hybrid halides remain significantly less explored than lead-based systems, particularly for electronic and memristive applications, where only one Zn-based hybrid memristor has been reported to date,^[29] underscoring the very early stage of this research direction. Developing new zinc iodide hybrid materials is therefore essential to expand the understanding of structure–property relationships and uncover emergent functionalities in this scarcely explored compositional space.

Here, we report the design, synthesis and characterization of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ (CHA = cyclohexylammonium), a new zinc iodide hybrid material composed of isolated inorganic tetrahedra and bulky organic cations. This material was prepared as single crystals, powders, and thin films under different processing conditions to investigate the structural and electronic

properties. Electrical characterization revealed resistive switching behaviour relevant for artificial synaptic functionalities, highlighting the potential of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ as an active material for neuromorphic devices and positioning Zn-based hybrids as promising platforms for next-generation electronic applications.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Synthesis

The cyclohexylammonium tetraiodozincate compound, $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ (CHA = cyclohexylammonium, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NH}_3^+$), was successfully prepared for the first time through a simple, scalable and environmentally friendly procedure at room temperature using water as solvent. The synthesis involves two steps, first the preparation of the cyclohexylammonium iodide salt (Scheme 1a), followed by its combination with zinc iodide in aqueous solution in a 2:1 molar ratio, (Scheme 1b) yielding suitable single crystals after slow evaporation at room temperature for 3 weeks (Details can be found in the Experimental Section).

In addition, a modified one-pot synthetic approach was also developed to obtain the material as a polycrystalline powder, significantly reducing the synthesis time. In contrast to the three-week slow evaporation process required for single-crystal growth, this rapid method enables efficient large-scale production. In this procedure, cyclohexylamine and zinc iodide were directly combined in a methanolic solution using the appropriate stoichiometric ratio. The resulting solution was then concentrated by rotary evaporation for 30 min, yielding the polycrystalline product in high yield.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of : a) cyclohexylammonium iodide b) $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$

2.2. Single crystal X-ray diffraction at different temperatures

Crystals suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD) were successfully obtained, and complete datasets were collected at two temperatures. The crystal structures collected at 100 and 293 K are essentially identical, with no evidence of a structural phase transition. However, the room-temperature dataset exhibits significantly enhanced thermal motion and disorder, reflected by substantially larger ellipsoids. This behavior suggests thermally activated dynamic disorder of the tetrahedral $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ units rather than a symmetry change. Due to the higher degree of disorder and the reduced structural precision at 293 K, the discussion below focuses primarily on the 100 K dataset but can be extended to the room temperature structure.

SCXRD studies revealed that the compound exhibits orthorhombic symmetry with space group $Pna2_1$ (non-centrosymmetric) and lattice parameters $a=12.51 \text{ \AA}$, $b=21.47 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=8.27 \text{ \AA}$ at $T=100 \text{ K}$ (see details in Table S1). The asymmetric unit consists of one $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ anion and two CHA cations as discrete ionic species (Figure S1). The Zn^{2+} cations are surrounded by four I^- anions in a tetrahedral coordination environment. The iodide anions are crystallographically disordered over two neighboring positions, indicating possible orientational disorder of the tetrahedral units, which could adopt two different orientations.

It is worth noting that the crystal structure reported here for $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ presents notable similarities with Ruddlesden–Popper (RP) type phases. The layered arrangement of $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra with interleaved organic cations is reminiscent of RP structures, in which perovskite-like inorganic slabs are separated by layers of organic or inorganic spacer cations. Furthermore, the stoichiometry of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ is consistent with that of RP phases of general formula A_2BX_4 , in where the polar ammonium groups of the CHA cations are oriented towards the inorganic component, establishing the $\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{I}$ hydrogen bonding interactions described above. Although the inorganic building unit consists of isolated $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra rather than corner-sharing octahedra as in classical RP perovskites, the overall structural motif alternating inorganic and organic layers with a directional organic–inorganic interface, places $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ within the broader family of RP-related layered hybrid materials.^[30]

The CHA cations exhibit two distinct crystallographic sites with different degrees of orientational disorder, that can be described as $\text{AA}'\text{BX}_4$. The first CHA cation (A) is fully ordered and adopts a chair conformation, see Figure S1. The second CHA cation (A') exhibits partial disorder: while the ammonium group occupies a single site, the cyclohexyl ring carbons

are distributed over two positions, corresponding to two closely related chair conformations, see Figure S1.

As it is shown on **Figure 1**, the crystal structure of this new compound can be visualized as an alternating stacking of layers along the b-axis: inorganic layers composed of $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra and organic layers of CHA cations. Within the inorganic layer, the $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra are arranged as discrete entities in a close-packed assembly, each being surrounded by six nearest neighbors, with intermolecular I··I separations between adjacent tetrahedra in the range of 4.0–4.4 Å (see Figure S2). The organic layers alternate with the inorganic layers along the b-axis, see Figure S3. Within the organic layers, the CHA cations adopt a close-packed arrangement with the ammonium groups oriented toward the inorganic layers along the b-axis and the cyclohexyl rings lying in the a-c plane. Each CHA cation is surrounded by six nearest neighbors. Examining the structure in the a-c plane reveals that the CHA cations display orientational ordering along chain-like arrangements running parallel to the a-axis. Two distinct types of chains can be identified: one composed of ordered and another composed of disordered CHA cations (A and A' respectively). These ordered and disordered chains alternate along the c-direction, see Figure S4.

Within each pair of adjacent ordered-disordered chains along the a-axis, the CHA cations exhibit slight tilting and displacement relative to each other, with their ammonium groups arranged in an antiparallel configuration along the b-axis, see Figure S4. Notably, all ammonium groups are cooperatively oriented in the same direction relative to their respective cyclohexyl rings. This cooperative alignment of the ammonium groups establishes a polar axis along the c-direction, which is responsible for the non-centrosymmetric nature of the crystal structure and spontaneous polarization, making the material pyroelectric and potentially ferroelectric.

Figure 1. Crystal structure of the $(\text{CHA})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ compound obtained by SCXRD at $T = 100$ K, viewed along the a - and c -axes.

Regarding the intermolecular interactions, the ammonium groups of the CHA cations are linked to the iodide anions of the $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra through hydrogen bonds. The $\text{N}\cdots\text{I}$ distances of 3.45 and 3.65 Å for the disordered and ordered CHA cations, respectively, are consistent with the presence of moderate $\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{I}$ hydrogen bonds, as these values fall within the typical range reported for ammonium iodide compounds (3.5–3.7 Å).^[31] These interactions likely contribute to the structural cohesion of the crystal packing.

In addition, the ordered CHA cations (A) occupy cavities created by four $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra: two tetrahedra belong to one chain running along the c -axis, while the other two belong to adjacent antiparallel chains. In contrast, the disordered CHA cations (A') are located in cavities formed by only three $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra, positioned between two adjacent chains, see Figure S4

2.3 Powder X-Ray Diffraction

Phase purity of the bulk material was assessed by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). The experimental diffractogram is in good agreement with the simulated pattern calculated from single-crystal data (see Figure S5), confirming that the target phase was always obtained as a pure material. Minor differences in relative peak intensities are attributed to preferred orientation effects in the powder sample. Specifically, the enhanced intensities of the $[0k0]$ Bragg peaks suggest that the crystallites preferentially orient with their $[010]$ planes parallel to

the sample surface. This crystallographic orientation is consistent with the distinctly acicular habit observed in the optical microscopy image (see **Figure 2a**).

2.4. Thermal characterization

Thermal stability of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) under an inert nitrogen atmosphere (see Figure S6). The compound remains thermally stable up to approximately 500 K, above which decomposition begins through a two-step process. The first mass loss, observed between 500 and 600 K, corresponds to a weight loss of ~60%, consistent with the release of two cyclohexylammonium iodide units. The second decomposition step, occurring between 600 and 680 K, accounts for a further mass loss of ~40%, attributed to the decomposition of the remaining inorganic ZnI_2 residue.

Therefore, the observed thermal stability up to ~500 K suggests that this material is sufficiently robust for practical applications at moderate temperatures.

2.5. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance Spectroscopy

The room-temperature UV–Vis spectrum of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ shows absorption below 500 nm, with two main maxima at ~264 and ~366 nm (Figure 2b). The higher-energy and more intense band at 264 nm can be attributed to high-energy electronic transitions within the material, while the feature at 366 nm appears to be associated with an excitonic transition. The optical band gap was estimated to be 2.3 eV by using the Kubelka-Munk equation (Figure 2b, inset).^[32] This value is considerably smaller than other reported 0D zinc halides such as $[\text{N-EPD}]_2\text{ZnBr}_4$ (4.11 eV)^[33] $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{N}]_2\text{ZnBr}_4$ (3.87 eV)^[34] $[\text{DPE}]\text{ZnCl}_4$ (3.27 eV)^[35] or $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)\text{ZnI}_4$ (4.25 eV)^[36] among others.

2.6. Polarization switching properties

At ambient temperature the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ displays a non-centrosymmetric space group with spontaneous polarization ($Pna2_1$ space group and [001] polarization edge). High voltage bipolar electric field experiments were thus conducted in hot-pressed pelletized samples in order to search for evidence of ferroelectric switching. **Figures 2c-2d** shows the polarization-electric field (P - E) and current density-electric field (I - E) hysteresis loops obtained at 10 Hz and electric field amplitudes from 20 to 120 kV cm⁻¹.

The P - E hysteresis loops obtained show cigar-shaped loops typical of non-ideal dielectric behavior, dominated by electrical losses, often called leaky loops. In such cases, any features of the loop that might be derived from polarization switching are overshadowed by leakage currents. These leakage currents are usually caused by mobile charge carriers in the material. As such there is no evidence of ferroelectric switching.^[37]

Figure 2. a) Optical microscopy image of the synthesized $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ acicular crystals. b) Room temperature absorption spectra between 200-900 nm of the $(\text{CHA})_2\text{ZnI}_4$. Inset represents the obtained Tauc plot with the calculated optical band gap. c) Polarization (P) hysteresis loops with an electric field frequency of 10 Hz and field amplitudes from 20 to 120 kV cm^{-1} d) Current density (I) hysteresis loops with electric field frequency of 10 Hz and field amplitudes from 20 to 120 kV cm^{-1}

In cases where the dielectric loss behaviour dominates the P - E loops, there can be additional information obtained from the I - E loops. Observing the I - E loops, we could visualize leakage current caused by both ohmic (linear as a function of electric field) and non-ohmic (non-linear as a function of electric field) conductivity. The ohmic conductivity is perhaps most easily identified in the loops at lower electric fields, 20 and 40 kV/cm , where the loops are angled

from the perfect horizontal with some gradient. The non-ohmic conductivity contributions are observed more clearly at higher fields 80-120 kV/cm, where the loop curves upwards with electric field nonlinearly. Additionally, ferroelectric materials typically exhibit current density peaks corresponding to the coercive field of domain switching as a signifier of ferroelectric behaviour. Such peaks are not distinguishable in this data and thus despite the application of electric fields up to 120 kV/cm there is no evidence that switching of the ferroelectric domains occurs.^[38]

Ferroelectric materials exhibit electromechanical coupling and thus the corresponding strain behavior as function of electric field also exhibits a distinct signature of ferroelectric switching.^[39] The S-E loops depicted at Figure S7 displayed only a signature of noise with specific frequency inherent to the experimental set up, with no distinguishable strain signal from the electromechanical response associated with the movement of the ferroelectric domains.

Despite having a non-centrosymmetric crystal structure with spontaneous polarization, the high electric field cycling study revealed a high electrical loss behavior of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ with no evidence of ferroelectric polarization switching. If the material can behave ferroelectrically the effect could be suppressed by the loss behavior in three ways. Firstly, any current signal from switching domains may be overshadowed by the high current density of the electrical loss. Secondly, the distribution of electric fields through conductive materials is known to be heterogeneous and thus several areas of the material may not have experienced the full magnitude of the electric field applied. Thirdly, the presence of charged defects that cause the conductivity, like cation or anion vacancies, may act as physical pinning centers that prevent ferroelectric domain walls from moving effectively and thus suppress switching. What this study does tell us however due to the high electrical loss and evidence of both ohmic and non-ohmic conductivity, is that the crystal structure of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ is likely able to sustain charged defects and thus nonstoichiometric. Loss behavior may thus be reduced by a careful optimization of synthesis or chemical modification of the composition. However, with their current electrical properties it is possible that the loss behavior itself may serve a function, in applications such as resistive memories.

2.7. Resistive switching and synaptic functionality

To assess the potential application of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ in resistive memories (memristor), we fabricated multi-layered stack devices with the structure: FTO/ $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ /PMMA/Ag. A

PMMA layer is placed between the material and the Ag contacts to regulate the migration of ions and hinder the reaction between silver and the OIMH^[40,41]. **Figure 3a** illustrates the device configuration. As described in the experimental section, (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] was deposited onto an FTO substrate using an antisolvent-assisted spin-coating method. The film retained the crystalline structure of the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] powder, according to XRD measurements (Figure S1). The SEM micrographs of the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] film (top view) reveal the formation of a flat homogeneous layer that crystallizes with no pinholes (**Figure 3b**).

The resistive switching properties were evaluated by measuring the I-V profiles. The voltage polarity is defined using the bottom FTO electrode as reference (grounded for stability). **Figure 3c** shows a representative I-V curve for the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] memristor, obtained at a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. The device shows inductive hysteresis at positive voltages, which is the feature associated with memory. At +0.6 V (SET voltage), the devices gradually switch from a high-resistance state (HRS) to a low-resistance state (LRS), with a change in current between 10⁻⁸ and approximately 10⁻⁵ A. Note that an electroforming step is not needed to trigger the hysteresis in the device. Different devices yield similar I-V profiles (Figure S8 a-c), proving device-to-device reproducibility. The SET/RESET voltages can shift hundreds of mV among devices, but the ON/OFF ratio and the separation between the SET and RESET voltages always remain similar. We also tested the variability of the I-V signal upon consecutive cycles, obtaining a constant response for at least (Figure S8 d), which is crucial for conducting a reliable analysis of the synaptic properties.

Figure 3. a) Scheme of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ memristor. b) SEM image of the top-view of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ layer. The inset shows an SEM in the same region with higher magnification. c) Representative I-V curve for the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ devices. LRS: low resistance state, HRS: high resistance state. d) Paired-pulse facilitation (PPF) index versus the interval time between paired pulses. The red line displays the fitting using a double-exponential decay function. e) Long-term potentiation (LTP) and long-term depression (LTD) curves obtained with a sequence of voltage pulses.

The synaptic plasticity of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ memristors was investigated by applying pulsed voltage biases, which is a type of signal that resembles the electrical stimuli that biological neurons use to communicate. We first investigated the paired-pulse facilitation (PPF) index to quantify the short-term synaptic plasticity (STP), which is one of the key dynamic behaviours

that artificial synapses should reproduce in neuromorphic hardware. The PPF index is defined as the increase in current caused by the application of two consecutive voltage pulses, which depends on the separation time existing between them. Paired voltage pulses must deliver different PPF index with different interval times (Δt). PPF is calculated as the ratio between the current measured during the second pulse (I_2) and the current during the first pulse (I_1), as described in **Equation 1** :

$$PPF_{Index} (\%) = \frac{I_2}{I_1} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Figure 3d shows the plot of PPF index versus interval time. The devices show a significant increase in conductance with short separation times, and the increase becomes negligible when the separation time is longer (> 600 s). The PPF index – Δt curve can be fitted using a double-exponential decay function (**Equation 2**):

$$PPF_{Index} (\%) = C_0 + C_1 \exp(-\Delta t/\tau_1) + C_2 \exp(-\Delta t/\tau_2) \quad (2)$$

Where C_0 represents the value to which the curve converges; C_1 and C_2 are the weights of the slow and fast paired-pulse facilitation phases, respectively; and τ_1 and τ_2 are the characteristic relaxation times of fast and slow processes, respectively.

The fitting of the experimental data resulted in the following relaxation times: $\tau_1 = 18$ ms and $\tau_2 = 427$ ms. These values are in the same range as those reported for other lead-free perovskite memristors^[42] and agree with the temporal dynamics of biological synapses. This demonstrates the STP of the FTO/(CHA)₂[ZnI₄]/PMMA/Ag memristors. After STP, the long-term plasticity was characterized. Long-term plasticity is achieved through prolonged STP training. We performed experiments in which consecutive excitatory (writing) and inhibitory (erasing) voltage pulses were applied to reproduce the synaptic functions long-term potentiation (LTP) and depression (LTD). **Figure 3e** shows the LTP and LTD curve, with the variation of conductance normalized to the interval between the minimum and maximum conductance. The LTP/LTD curves are constructed upon the application of 50 consecutive pulses of +1 V and 100 ms, followed by equivalent 50 pulses at the reverse polarity (-1 V). The read voltage was +0.1 V in both cases. The curves show a long-term increase in conductance with the application

of positive voltage pulses that can be modulated by the number, and a similar decrease in conductance when -1 V pulses are applied. The LTP/LTD curve is repeatable for several consecutive cycles with no significant changes (Figure S9). However, the profile of the LTP/LTD curves is not optimal since the variation of conductance is not completely linear, indicating that further optimization of the device's architecture is needed, which will be the scope of a follow-up work. The results reflect the potential of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ hybrid material to be used as an active material for the fabrication of memristors for memory applications and artificial synapses in neuromorphic computing hardware.

3. Conclusion

Here, we report the synthesis and structural characterization of a novel hybrid compound, $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ (CHA = cyclohexylammonium), prepared through a simple, scalable, and environmentally friendly route at room temperature using water as the sole solvent. By single-crystal X-ray diffraction, we have elucidated the crystal structure of this compound, which crystallizes in the non-centrosymmetric orthorhombic space group $Pna2_1$, comprising isolated $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra and a cooperative alignment of the polar organic cations that generates a polar axis along $[001]$. Despite its zero-dimensional inorganic framework, $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ adopts a layered architecture reminiscent of Ruddlesden–Popper-type phases, with the polar ammonium groups of the CHA cations directed toward the inorganic component.

Motivated by the non-centrosymmetric polar structure of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$, we investigated its potential ferroelectric behavior through high electric field cycling. However, the P–E, I–E and S–E loops collectively reveal significant leakage currents and the absence of ferroelectric domain switching at fields up to 120 kV/cm. Indicating that the relatively high electrical conductivity of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ would need to be controlled by synthesis or compositional engineering in order to probe the potential ferroelectric properties further.

Taking advantage of this conductivity and of the ability of the material to be easily nanostructured into thin films by spin-coating, we integrated it into multilayer FTO/ $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ /PMMA/Ag devices, which demonstrate stable and reproducible memristive behavior without requiring an electroforming step and with well-defined switching between high- and low-resistance states at low operating voltages. Beyond memory effects, the material exhibits key features of synaptic functionality. The devices exhibit short-term synaptic plasticity, evidenced by paired-pulse facilitation with biologically relevant relaxation times, as

well as long-term potentiation and depression under pulsed operation. Although further optimization is needed to achieve linear conductance modulation, these results establish $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ as a promising lead-free candidate for memory and neuromorphic applications. The combination of green synthesis, structural versatility, and functional device integration opens new possibilities for the development of lead-free materials, and highlights the largely unexplored potential of Zn-based systems in next-generation electronic devices.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Commercially available cyclohexylamine ($\geq 99.9\%$ w/w, Aldrich), stabilized hydroiodic acid solution, HI, (57% w/w, Acros Organics) and zinc iodide ($\geq 98\%$, Aldrich) were used as starting materials without any previous purification. Solvents such as N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous, 99.8%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, anhydrous, 99.9%), and chlorobenzene (anhydrous, 99.8%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. FTO/glass substrates were purchased from Pilkington ($15 \Omega/\text{cm}^2$).

Synthesis: In order to obtain the cyclohexylammonium hybrid halides, the synthesis was performed in two steps:

Synthesis of the $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NH}_3)\text{I}$ (CHAD): Cyclohexylamine halide salt was obtained by neutralizing a methanolic solution of cyclohexylamine and a small excess of the halide acid ($\sim 5\%$ molar excess). The obtained mixture was concentrated until dryness using a rotatory evaporator until a white/yellowish polycrystalline powder was obtained.

Synthesis of the $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NH}_3)_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ hybrid compound: The hybrid halide compound was prepared by mixing an aqueous solution of the previous synthesized cyclohexylamine halide salt with another aqueous solution containing the zinc iodide compound in ratio (2:1) and 0.5M concentration. The mixture was left to evaporate at room temperature. After 3 weeks of slow evaporation, suitable single crystals were formed. The crystals were isolated by filtration and washed several times with diethyl ether.

Device fabrication: Memristors were fabricated by an optimized protocol consisting of several steps to provide the stack structure FTO/ $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ /PMMA/Ag.

Substrates cleaning: First, FTO (F:SnO₂) substrates were chemically etched using Zn powder and hydrochloric acid (HCl) to define conductive patterns. Prior to the material deposition, the etched substrates were cleaned by being immersed in an ultrasonic bath with water + detergent, Acetone, and Isopropyl alcohol sequentially (10 min each). After cleaning, the substrates are

placed inside an ultraviolet (UV)-ozone chamber for 15 min to further clean the FTO surface. Before the fabrication, the so-cleaned substrates are transferred into a glovebox.

(CHA)₂[ZnI₄] layer deposition: We deposited the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] hybrid material layer onto the FTO substrates by spin-coating a solution of 0.3 M of the material in a mixture of DMF/DMSO (volumetric ratio 4:1). Spin coating was performed in two steps: 1) 1000 rpm for 10 s and 2) 4000 rpm for 30 s. Toluene as an antisolvent was added 8 seconds after the start of the second step to remove the excess of solvent and enable the proper crystallization of (CHA)₂[ZnI₄]. The spin-coated (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] film was left to dry overnight at room temperature inside the glovebox. The dry films had a light blue color.

PMMA layer: A thin PMMA layer (50 nm) was deposited on top of the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] layer by spin-coating a 10 mg mL⁻¹ PMMA solution in chlorobenzene onto the Glass/FTO/(CHA)₂[ZnI₄] device at 4000 rpm for 30 s.

Ag contact deposition: The Ag top contacts were prepared by thermal evaporation of silver (70 nm) through three steps: 0-1 nm thick Ag: 0.5 Å s⁻¹, 1-10 nm thick Ag: 1 Å s⁻¹, and 10-70 nm thick Ag: 5 Å s⁻¹

Single crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD): Single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD) experiments were carried out at T= 100 and 293 K. For that purpose, single-crystal diffraction data sets were collected in a Bruker D8 VENTURE Kappa X-ray diffractometer equipped with a PHOTON III detector and using monochromatic AgK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.56086$ Å). The crystal was mounted on MiTeGen MicroMount™ using Paratone® N (Hampton Research). The data integration and reduction were performed using the APEX4 v2021.10-0 software suite.^[43] The integrations of the reflections were performed with SAINT 8.40B^[44] and the intensities collected were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects and for absorption by semi-empirical methods on the basis of symmetry-equivalent data using SADABS 2016/2 of the suite software.^[45] The structures were solved by the dual-space algorithm implemented in SHELXT2014/5 program and were refined by least squares method on SHELXL2018/3.^[46,47] (Table S1).

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD): A Siemens D-5000 diffractometer and a D8 Advance Diffractometer (Bruker-AXS), using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418$ Å), were employed to study the (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] obtained powder and the built memristor by PXRD at room temperature respectively. The obtained diffractograms were compared with the profiles obtained by single crystal data of the corresponding phase in each case generated by using Mercury 4.2.0,^[48]

proving that the phase of interest had been obtained in each case (see Figure S5). Differences between intensities are related to preferred orientations in the powder samples.

Thermal analysis: Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the $(\text{CHA})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ material was carried out in a NETZSCH STA 499 F3 Jupiter. Approximately 30 mg of powder sample were heated at a rate of 10 K min^{-1} from 298 to 873 K using a corundum crucible under a constant flow of dry nitrogen.

UV-Vis diffuse reflectance Spectroscopy: Optical diffuse reflectance measurements of the polycrystalline powder samples were performed at room temperature using a Jasco V-730 UV-vis double-beam spectrophotometer with a single monochromator, operating from 200 to 900 nm. BaSO_4 was used as a non-absorbing reflectance reference. The generated reflectance versus wavelength data were used to estimate the band gap of the material by converting reflectance to absorbance data according to the Kubelka–Munk equation:^[32] $F(R) = \alpha = (1 - R)^2/2R$, where R is the reflectance data and α values are the absorption coefficients

Scanning electronic microscopy (SEM): Spin coated films of $(\text{CHA})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ were characterized (top view) by SEM using a JEOL 7001F scanning electron microscope operated at 15 kV with a secondary electrons (SE) detector. The samples were coated with a thin layer of Pt due to the low conductivity of the $(\text{CHA})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.

Polarization-Electric field (P-E) hysteresis measurements: P-E hysteresis measurements were carried out at room temperature in a Aixacct ferroelectric tester equipped with a TReK 10 KV signal amplifier and a laser interferometer for strain measurements. A triangular waveform at frequencies from 0.1 to 100 Hz was used for hysteresis measurements up to 120 kV/cm. All samples used were polycrystalline powder that had been hot pressed into dense pellets at temperatures of 85°C and a small pressure of approximately 10 MPa using a heated plate press. Gold electrodes were deposited by sputter deposition on the opposite surfaces of the pellet using a shadow mask.

Current-voltage measurements: All electrical measurements of the $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ -based device were carried out inside the glovebox. Current-voltage measurements (cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry) were performed using a Metrohm's Autolab PGSTAT204 coupled with Nova 2.1 software.

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Data Availability Statement

CCDC 2555355 and 2555354 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif

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Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

A Novel Polar Zinc-based Hybrid Material: Structure, Properties, and Memristive Performance

A new hybrid zinc halide, $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$, is introduced as a sustainable memristive material. The compound combines a polar zero-dimensional structure with stable electroforming-free resistive switching and synaptic plasticity at low voltages. These findings highlight the potential of Zn-based hybrid halides for neuromorphic computing and next-generation memory devices.

ToC figure